

Educating the Educators: A Comprehensive Study of Teaching Practices in Quetta's Teacher Training Institutions through the Lens of National Professional Standards

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ABSTRACT: Purpose: The objective of this study is to evaluate the effectiveness of teacher professional development programs during practicum, specifically focusing on the analysis of the impact of National Professional Teaching Standards (NPTS) in teacher training institutions located in Baluchistan. The National Professional Teaching Standards (NPTS) establish a comprehensive framework of benchmarks and anticipated outcomes that educators are encouraged to fulfill. By adhering to these standards, teachers can increase their instructional methodologies and ultimately enhance the academic achievements of their students.

Design/Methodology: The present study utilizes a quantitative research methodology to collect data from educators in the region of Baluchistan. The participants in this study were educators who have completed practicum placements and have been exposed to the National Professional Teaching Standards (NPTS). The NPTS indicators were assessed using a survey questionnaire, which was provided to the prospective teachers. The survey evaluated multiple dimensions of teachers' professional growth, encompassing their knowledge, abilities, and attitudes pertaining to teaching practice. The data obtained from the survey was subjected to analysis using statistical methods, namely descriptive statistics, Pearson Correlation and Simple Linear Regression.

Findings: The study's findings contain substantial consequences for educational policymakers and stakeholders. The findings of this study demonstrated that National Professional Teaching Standards (NPTS) impacts on prospective teachers' growth and development during practicum experiences in Baluchistan. Specifically the findings of this study indicated that there is a statistically significant, positive and strong relationship between the growth and development, subject matter knowledge, instructional planning strategies and assessment. Hence, results revealed that hypotheses of current research study were rejected.

Implications: The study's results produced significant insights on the efficacy of the NPTS in facilitating teacher professional development. By assessing the impact of NPTS on teacher training and support programs, this research will contribute to the current body of literature on effective teaching practices. Furthermore, it will provide evidence-based recommendations for enhancing teacher training and development programs.

Key words: National Professional Teaching Standards, practicum, professional development.

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1. Introduction

This study's background relates to how crucial professional development for teachers is to raising student achievement and educational outcomes. Pakistan's National Professional Teaching Standards (NPTS) were created with the goal of offering a disciplined framework for enhancing teacher professional development. Still, there is a dearth of thorough knowledge about how these standards impact teaching strategies and ultimately impact student learning outcomes. This study's primary goal is to close the existing research gap by examining how Newly Qualified Teacher Support (NPTS) affects teachers' professional growth while they are completing their practicums in Baluchistan. This study's main goal is to investigate how teacher practice and the National Professional Teaching Standards (NPTS) relate to one another. The goal is to offer practical advice on how to better support and foster teacher professional development. This study mainly focuses on three National Professional Teaching Standards (NPTS) such as subject matter knowledge, instructional planning and strategies and assessment. Therefore, this investigates the relationship between these three National Professional Teaching Standards (NPTS) such as subject matter knowledge, instructional planning and strategies and assessment with prospective teachers' growth and development (Rehan, et al., 2024).

There is currently a limited amount of knowledge available about how the National Professional Teaching Standards (NPTS) affect teachers' professional development during their practicum experiences in Baluchistan. One of the biggest challenges to improving student learning outcomes and teacher quality is a lack of understanding. Examining the effect of NPTS on teachers' professional development during practicum experiences is the main goal of this study. The goal is to offer important insights into the most effective strategies for bolstering and improving teaching quality.

Research Objectives

General Objective:

This analysis aims to identify particular areas within the NPTS framework that could be enhanced to provide better support for teacher growth and development during practicum experiences in the teacher training institutions of Baluchistan.

Specific Objectives"

1. To investigate the correlation between National Professional Teaching Standards (NPTS) subject matter and prospective teachers' growth and development in Baluchistan.

2. To find out the relationship between National Professional Teaching Standards (NPTS) instructional planning and strategies and prospective teachers' growth and development Baluchistan.
3. To examine the relationship between National Professional Teaching Standards (NPTS) assessment and prospective teachers' growth and development in Baluchistan.

Research questions

1. What is the impact of implementing the National Professional Teaching Standards (NPTS) such as subject matter knowledge, instructional planning and strategies and assessment on prospective teachers' growth and development in Baluchistan?

Research Hypothesis

1. There is no any correlation between National Professional Teaching Standard (NPTS) subject matter and prospective teachers' growth and development in Baluchistan.
2. National Professional Teaching Standard (NPTS) instructional planning and strategies has not significant relationship with prospective teachers' growth and development in Baluchistan.
3. There is no any relationship between National Professional Teaching Standards (NPTS) assessment and prospective teachers' growth and development in Baluchistan.

Problem Statement

Ensuring high standards in the preparation of teachers is critical for the effective professional practice of the teacher (Ananga, 2021). Because of this, the National Professional Teaching Standards was introduced. The National Professional Teaching Standards represents the first ever collectively agreed standards to guide teacher preparation and education practice (Kelvin, 2021). The Standards have been developed as a professional tool to guide teacher educators, student-teachers and other stakeholders in education to identify in clear and precise terms what teachers are expected to know and be able to do, qualities they are expected to possess and some behaviour they are supposed to exhibit. However, it was studied in previous literature that a few studies were carried on relationship between National Professional Teaching Standards (NPTS) and prospective teachers' growth and development, especially in Baluchistan. This study however focused on the relationship between National Professional Teaching standards and student teachers' growth and development in Baluchistan.

2. Literature Review

Revamping the Education System

The quality of teacher education has always been emphasized by the government in its different policies. The Government of Pakistan has established National Professional Teaching Standards (NPTS) to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of teaching among

teachers. With the assistance of United States Agency for International Development (USAID) the policy and planning wing Ministry of Education launched Strengthening Teacher Education in Pakistan. By developing National Professional Teaching Standards education and teacher growth and development has significantly been influenced in schools (UNESCO, 2020). National Professional Teaching Standards establish a comprehensive framework of benchmarks and anticipated outcomes that educators are encouraged to fulfill. By adhering to these standards, teachers can increase their instructional methodologies and ultimately enhance the academic achievements of their students. Teachers can apply these standards to improve their teaching skills. The purpose of creating the National Professional Standards for Teachers (NPST) in 2009 was to give professional teachers and educators precise guidelines for their duties and assisting them in self-evaluating their professional development. These standards cover performance and abilities, attitudes, and knowledge and comprehension. Skills, development, and promotion are discussed. The following rules apply to teachers and educational establishments. The importance of teaching these values should be given top priority in teacher workshops (Khan & Aleem, 2014). More people are becoming aware of the importance of education and high-quality teachers in recent years.

Revisions to teacher training criteria have been implemented globally in an attempt to enhance the quality of teachers and the effectiveness of their methods (Iqbal et al., 2011). In recent years, teacher education has become a hot topic of discussion in developing countries. Professional standards are being implemented in a number of sectors as a result of the increased focus on high-quality education across the globe. Scholars have endeavored to acquire a more profound comprehension of educators' ideas, expertise, understanding, and professional behaviors (Ingvarson, 1998; Kennedy, 2015).

The process of defining and adopting professional standards for teachers is presently underway in the United States, the United Kingdom, and several other industrialized nations, according to the National Education Association. Tuinamuna et al. (2011) state that these countries are motivated by policy goals that maintain that raising professional standards will improve the caliber of teachers in those nations.

Pakistan has made improving teacher education a top policy priority ever since gaining independence in 1947. After academic training programs were established in Britain, there was a noticeable shift in focus toward these programs in the United States and other countries during the first few decades of the twenty-first century. A large number of formal educational institutions were established during the 1980s. The Allama Iqbal Open University (AIU) was founded with the intention of providing informal learning opportunities to the general public through remote education. The most significant reforms to teacher education in Pakistan since the nation's independence were marked by the introduction of the Primary Teaching Certificate (PTC) and Certificate of Teaching (CT) in the mid-2000s.

It is clear from academic literature, stories from the media and mainstream, feedback from foreign funders, and statements from international organizations working in Pakistan that the teacher education programs currently in place in Pakistan have produced teachers who are not well-prepared for their positions. The number of aspiring teachers is rising annually, but their knowledge of the subject and level of experience are lacking, according

to the authors (2020). As a result, the Government of Pakistan (2017) has identified improving the quality of teacher education as a critical area of emphasis for Pakistan's upcoming 2017 Education Policy, which is currently being formulated.

This project will include the revision of outdated teacher education programs and their replacement with more modern, structured options. In order to meet the National Standards for Teachers, professional development courses will be made available to aspiring teachers (Chang, 2014). Arif et al. (2012) state that, among other things, incorporating empathy and interpersonal skills into teacher preparation or education programs can increase the efficacy of teachers.

Akram et al. (2015) have documented the concerns expressed by established interest groups and various stakeholders regarding teacher education in Pakistan over a period of several years. They believe that there has not been enough done by the Pakistani government to improve the state of teacher preparation for the classroom of the future. According to the authors (Ali et al., 2011), the training they received through various programs is not in line with resources, curriculum materials, school environments, or the common entrance requirements for teacher education programs. As a result, educators use insufficient information and communication technology (ICT) and demonstrate insufficient teaching competencies and instructional strategies. This results in inadequate preparation for class meetings, a lack of awareness of how children learn, and a poor execution of educational initiatives (Iqbal & Shams, 2012; Iqbal, Qureshi, Ashraf, Rasool, & Asghar, 2021). To achieve improvements, all teachers must be well-versed in the perspectives of the world, demonstrate a high level of preparedness, provide ongoing professional development, and provide critical support to children and their families. Following the guidelines established by the National Board for Professional Teaching Standards is essential for everyone involved in the education of students (Iqbal & Arif, 2011).

As a result, with help from USAID (the United States Agency for International Development), the Pakistani Ministry of Education created ten National Professional Standards for Primary School Teachers. The effective date of these guidelines was February 23, 2009. It is unclear if these standards are followed with the same fervor and enthusiasm as expected, despite the fact that they serve as the cornerstone of excellent instruction. An attempt has been made to assess the teachers at the eight chosen circles in the KP district Peshawar using the previously mentioned standards.

The educational system in question offers educators numerous chances to enhance their abilities via cooperative efforts and permits them to participate in the formulation of policies (Wei, R. C., Andree, A., & Darling-Hammond, L. 2009). Professionalism is encouraged everywhere in the world, but it is especially emphasized in the educational system since it is so important. Raising the bar for teaching standards, requiring greater subject-matter expertise, a serious demeanor, classroom experience, and many other requirements, is how professionalism is developed (Kramer, 2003). Additionally, ongoing research is conducted to identify fresh approaches to enhancing the classroom setting, instructional strategies, and simple teaching methods—all of which contribute to the growth of professionalism (Darling-Hammond & Bransford, 2005). One of the most well-known occupations in Pakistan is teaching, which accounts for a sizable portion of the workforce in

the public education system (Hussain, 2005). Education policies are developed with consideration for social development, professional values, and morality. In order to select teachers who meet higher standards, the requirements for becoming a teacher have been raised (Ahmad, et al., 2024; Anwar, 2005). The country's efforts to promote professionalism and bring education standards up to par with international norms have benefited greatly from the implementation of national educational policies and National Professional Standards for Teachers (NPSTs). The general success of a student is observed to be significantly influenced by their education.

According to (Rahim Khan) "The Growth of a nation depends upon the progress of its citizens. The improvement of its people depends upon the expansion of their education; the growth of their education depends upon the development of their educators."¹ "The excellence of education is straight connected to the excellence of teaching in the classroom. The educator is measured the most essential factor in executing all education reforms at the grassroots level. It is a fact that the academic educations, the teaching-learning process is significantly impacted by the teacher's subject-matter expertise, teaching abilities, and dedication. The efficacy of teacher education programs and the professional development of the nation's in-service teachers need to be given sufficient precedence in light of the declining quality of education at various levels. The most substantial agency to bring basic and creative changes in the teaching-learning process are educators and they are the hub of the whole educational system. All-round efforts are needed to produce reflective and artistic educators who are holistically trained through a continuing professional development process. It is a fact that educators are the key agent of change, as they transform and rebuild the whole education systems through adopting and integrated meaningful techniques in the class room. Kennedy, the late president of America has declared educator as the main support of a society. He said, "If you overlook professional development of a teacher in fact you ignore the whole nation." teaching holds a prominent position in a society, teaching profession, being foundation of all remaining professions that's why there is a scorching need to make the teacher well equipped with the latest instructional strategies to meet the rising strains of this profession. To fulfill the increasing demands of the education profession world has started gallant steps for professional development of teachers. Standard based improvement of educators is the main program of international movement. As Primary education inhabits the most important place in holistic and all-round development of an individual and achievement at higher levels depends upon the efficiency of the primary education.

Quality in teacher education has always been a policy issue in Pakistan since it became an independent state in 1947, though for the first few decades it was primarily based on the British model of post-academic training programs. The 1980s saw the establishment of a number of formal teacher education institutions, such as the Provincial Institutes of Teacher Education (PITE), as well as informal training through distance learning, such as the Allama Iqbal Open University (AIU). However, the introduction of teacher education certification and diplomas like the Primary Teaching Certificate (PTC) and Certificate in Teaching (CT) in the middle of the 2000s marked the most significant shift in Pakistani teacher education. In the current landscape of teacher training, pre-service teacher education programs were introduced in collaboration with USAID. These programs

offer qualifications like an Associate Degree in Education and a Bachelor of Education (Honors), as well as some advanced diplomas and certificates in teacher education (Imran, et al., 2023).

The teacher is the focal point of the entire educational system and the most significant agent for bringing about change. It is still true that educators are the agents of change because, within their classrooms, they apply cutting edge and integrated methods to reshape and modernize the educational system. Professional development for educators is just as vital as survival (Khan, Hussain & Ahmad, 2023). A teacher devoid of the proper education is akin to a body devoid of spirit. John F. Kennedy, the late president of the United States, believed that educators were the cornerstone of society. "In fact, you ignore the e," he said. It is vital to provide teachers with the newest instructional strategies to meet the increasing demands of this profession, as teaching is the cornerstone of all other professions and occupies a significant position in society. The globe has made dramatic strides to enhance teachers' professional development to fulfill the expanding demands of the teaching profession. The international movement's primary objective is to raise teaching standards.

Relationship of National Professional Standards for Teachers (NPST) and Growth and Development of Teachers

In the current study, three standards have been adopted including Subject matter knowledge, Assessment, and Instructional Planning and Strategies and their impact on growth and development of Prospective Teacher.

Subject Matter knowledge and growth and development of Prospective Teacher

The teacher subject matter is a matter on which the teachers are recruited to continue their teaching. Teacher grip and common on subject can carry on positive change in his teaching career. Teachers with basic understanding of their subject contents are the cornerstone of pedagogical material knowledge that makes them meaningful teacher (Shulman et al., 2021). Moreover, Rice (2003) emphasized that teachers in-depth topic knowledge can make students engaged and create respect for teacher among students. A study conducted by Ball (2010) stated that teachers need to be modernized regarding comprehension in their respective subjects which can improve their growth and development (Imran & Akhtar, 2023).

Assessment and growth and development of Prospective Teacher

According to a Paper on teacher assessment (2010) from National Education Association (NEA) defined that the purpose of assessment is twofold which improve teachers practice and enhance skills. Mostly, teachers use formal and informal assessment in classroom to check what students learnt and what material covered (Ahmed, Ahmed & Buriro, 2023). Furthermore, assessment can help teacher to determine which effective teaching strategies should be used to teach any topics. Assessment also reflects teachers' performance and guide in professional growth and development. Moreover, assessment

provides additional opportunities for teachers to learn and grow to become prospective teacher (Ali, et al., 2023).

Instructional Planning and Strategies for the growth and development of Prospective Teacher

Instructional planning and strategies are the most significant standard of National professional standards which help teachers to visualize and forecast into the future of what, why and how the teaching process should be carried out in classroom. Khalid et al. (2022) concluded that most of teachers adopt the application of Instructional Planning and Strategies with need for improvement in the skills development aspect. Instructional Planning and Strategies proved effective in raising the performance, growth, and development of teachers. Moreover, Vanassche and Kelchtermans (2014) stated that Instructional Planning and Strategies is the key contribution to the development of teachers in their professional life (Mohammad, et al., 2024).

Challenges faced by teachers.

Lack of knowledge and comprehension of the national professional standards is one of the difficulties teachers encounter when putting them into practice. According to a study by Khalid, Anwar, and Musawir (2020), a large number of Pakistani teachers are unaware of the national professional standards. This ignorance can be linked to the teachers' limited access to professional development opportunities and inadequate training, which made it challenging for them to incorporate the standards into their lesson plans (Imran, Sultana, & Ahmed, 2023).

Another challenge faced by teachers in implementing national professional standards is the lack of support from the government and educational institutions. A study by Naqvi, Fatima, and Hameed (2020) found that teachers in Pakistan faced several challenges, including lack of resources and support from the government and educational institutions. This lack of support can hinder the implementation of national professional standards, as teachers may not have access to the necessary resources to implement the standards effectively (Hussain, et al., 2023).

Moreover, the application of national professional standards may face difficulties due to Baluchistan's cultural and societal norms. According to a study by Ahmad and Ali (2018), cultural elements like gender roles and beliefs can affect how professional standards for teachers are implemented. For instance, cultural barriers may make it difficult for female teachers to take advantage of professional development opportunities, which may impair their capacity to successfully apply the standards (Hafeez, Iqbal, & Imran, 2021).

Conceptual Framework

This research is about relationship between national professional teaching standards such as subject matter knowledge, instructional planning strategies and assessment with student teachers' growth and development. This conceptual framework shows the relationship between independent and dependent variables. The dependent variable is

student teachers' growth and development and the independent variables are subject matter knowledge, instructional planning and strategies and assessment

The above conceptual framework is based on the De Bueger and Vander Borgh (1996) theory.

This research focused to investigate the relationship between the independent variables and dependent variable and how national professional teaching standards (NPTS) are diagrammatically associated with student teachers' growth and development in Balochistan. NPTS (Subject matter knowledge, assessment and instructional planning and strategies) enhance prospective teachers' growth and development. The above framework shows that subject matter knowledge, assessment and instructional planning and strategies are independent variables and prospective teachers' growth and development is dependent variable (Phulpoto, Oad, & Imran, 2024).

In conclusion, there are several obstacles that the Quetta District's higher education institutions must overcome in order to successfully implement the national professional standards for teachers. These obstacles include a lack of knowledge and comprehension of the standards, a lack of support from the government and other educational institutions, and cultural and societal norms. Teachers, government representatives, and educational institutions must work together to address these issues and provide the resources and support required to guarantee the standards are implemented successfully.

3. Methodology

The research methodology covers research design, population, sampling, instrumentation and procedure of data collection for the current study. This study looks at the practicum experiences of pre-service teachers in teacher training institutions in Baluchistan. Baluchistan is home to teacher training facilities, educator institutes, and both private and public schools that are funded. The academic year study demonstrates how pre-service teachers' professional development is impacted by the National Professional Teaching Standards.

Research Design

In order to investigate how the National Professional Teaching Standards (NPTS) impact teachers' professional development during their practicum in Baluchistan, this study employs a quantitative methodology. This research study was quantitative in nature because the aim of this study was to investigate the relationship and impact of National Professional Teaching Standard (NPTS). Specifically three National Professional Teaching Standard (NPTS) such as subject matter knowledge, instructional planning and strategies and assessment were included in this study. Therefore, objectives of this study were fulfilling by using quantitative research study. To do this, an adapted survey is used. The National Professional Teaching Standards (NPTS) and frameworks for teacher professional development are in line with this survey. During practicums, it gathers information from a representative sample of prospective teachers. Evaluation of alternative professional development and pre-service teacher development is made simpler by the design.

Population and Sampling

The sample includes 162 future teachers selected by random sampling among 280 Baluchistan teacher training college students. The eligibility requirements include practicum work at a Baluchistan public or private school and acquaintance with the National Professional Teaching Standards.

Research Instruments

This study used a pretested survey questionnaire. This questionnaire follows NPTS and teacher professional development standards. Its goal is to collect demographic data and study NPTS conceptual frameworks, focusing on subject matter expertise, instructional preparation, and tactics.

Validity

A pilot study was carried out at the Baluchistan Teachers Training College to validate the questionnaire. In two or three situations, a researcher can carry out a pilot study, according to Borg & Gall (1989). The preliminary test was designed to assist the researcher in determining which elements were deemed inappropriate and making the necessary corrections. It also looked at the answers to see how ambiguous the questions were, and it assessed participant responses to calculate a percentage. The unclear items were changed to better fits their new configurations. It was useful in figuring out how long it would take to operate the instrument. The research determined which 35 questions from the questionnaire should be administered after consulting with experts. According to Gay, L. R. (1987), the descriptive survey research method entails data collection in order to assess hypotheses or provide answers regarding the study's current state.

Reliability

The reliability demonstrates the consistency of result in the survey. Therefore, statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) was used to ensure the reliability of the survey tool. The alpha value should be .7 or above for the reliable tool.

Data Analysis

Statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) software was used to analyze the results for this quantitative research study. Mean, standard deviation, Pearson Correlation and Simple Linear Regression analysis techniques were used to check the hypothesis for this study.

Findings and Analysis

The analysis was conducted in form of frequency and percentages. Result is presented in the table as under:

Table 1

Items	Frequency	Percentage
Prospective teacher clearly understand aims and objectives of the subject which she/he teaches.	80	86.4
Prospective teacher possesses up-to-date knowledge of all basic concepts and theories of the subject	76	71.6
Prospective teacher possesses knowledge of history and process of acquiring knowledge of the subject	60	59.3
Prospective teacher keeps his/herself up to date with new ideas and latest trends of the subject	62	82.7
Prospective teacher shares new knowledge and theories emerging at national level related to the subject	78	71.6
Prospective teacher shares new theories and results of the research done at international level related to the subject	62	58.1
Prospective teacher develops the link between his/her teaching subjects with other disciplines	54	56.8
Prospective teacher easily incorporates real life experiences in his/her teaching subject	56	58.1
Prospective teacher knows and understand aims, goals and objectives of education and guide students related to them	66	76.5
Prospective teacher shares the aims goals and objective with students and guide in this regard	84	72.9
Prospective teacher teaches writing skills at different stages of development	72	62.9
Prospective Teacher Teaches Arithmetic Skills Stages of Development	78	66.6
Prospective teacher makes link new knowledge to student priori knowledge	52	42
Prospective teacher uses different relevant teaching approaches for different topics	56	64.2
Prospective teacher has knowledge about the proper use of resources and material for instructional planning	68	64.2
Prospective teacher uses technological resources to increase attention of students	62	66.7
Prospective teacher assigns homework to class related to class lesson	64	69.1

Prospective teacher assigns different activities to class related to class Lesson	84	67.9
Prospective teacher uses instructional strategies based on students need and age /level	68	71.6
Prospective teacher uses different teaching methods for slow learners	58	71.6
Prospective teacher plan and modify different instructional approaches to promote students' attention	72	65.4
Prospective teacher engages class in question-answering that help students to learn	76	77.8
Prospective teacher use activities in classroom that help students to learn	58	65.4
Prospective teacher possesses sufficient knowledge about effective classroom management	46	61.7
Prospective teacher has sufficient knowledge of all assessment techniques	62	66.7
Prospective teacher assigns class presentations to students	82	81.5
Prospective teacher assigns projects to students	56	59.3
Prospective teacher assigns more numbers to his/her favorite students	40	42
Prospective Teacher Uses Objective Type Tests for Student Assessment	56	53.1
Prospective Teacher Uses Subjective Type of Tests for Student Assessment	70	58
Prospective teacher uses different types of questions i.e., mcqs, short answer and essay questions in test	56	66.7
Prospective Teacher Gives to Student Complete Feedback about Their Performance in Assessment	82	76.5
Prospective teacher uses class feedback to improve his/her teaching strategies	56	61.8
Prospective teacher maintains proper record of his/her student performance	56	72.9

The survey found that 86.4% of prospective instructors agree with their comprehensive understanding of the subjects they teach, while 5.8% exhibit confusion or disagreement. A significant portion (71.6%) believe they possess up-to-date knowledge of all basic concepts and theories, while 12.3% show uncertainty or disagreement. A significant portion (59.2%) also possess knowledge of the history and process of acquiring knowledge of the subject. Only 11.1% express uncertainty or disagreement. A significant portion (82.7%) keep themselves updated with new ideas and trends, while 6.2% express uncertainty or disagreement. A significant portion (71.6%) share new knowledge and theories emerging at the national level related to the subject, while only 9.9% express uncertainty or disagreement.

A majority of prospective teachers (58.1%) believe they share new theories and research results related to their subject, while a small percentage (16%) express

uncertainty or disagreement. 56.8% believe they link their teaching subjects with other disciplines, while a small percentage (16%) express uncertainty or disagreement. 58.1% easily incorporate real-life experiences into their teaching, while a small percentage (19.7%) express uncertainty or disagreement. 76.5% of prospective teachers understand the aims, goals, and objectives of education and guide students, while a small percentage (11.1%) express uncertainty or disagreement. 72.9% agree to share these aims, goals, and objectives with students, while a small percentage (13.6%) express uncertainty or disagreement.

A majority of prospective teachers (62.9%) believe they teach reading and writing skills at different stages of development, while a small percentage (13.3%) express uncertainty and disagreement. A significant percentage (42%) teach arithmetic skills at different stages, while a small percentage (19.7%) express uncertainty and disagreement. A significant percentage (64.2%) link student new knowledge with prior knowledge, while a small percentage (9.9%) express uncertainty and disagreement. Additionally, a significant percentage (64.2%) use different teaching approaches for different topics, while a small percentage (16%) express uncertainty and disagreement.

The majority of prospective teachers (66.7%) believe they have knowledge about proper resource and material use for instructional planning, while a small percentage (18.5%) express uncertainty and disagreement. 69.1% use technological resources to increase student attention, while 18.5% express uncertainty. 67.9% assign homework related to class lessons, while 8.6% express uncertainty. 71.6% assign different activities related to class lessons, while 16.1% express uncertainty. Lastly, 71.6% use instructional strategies based on student needs and age/level, while 9.8% express uncertainty and disagreement. These findings highlight the need for more effective instructional strategies for teachers.

A majority of prospective teachers (67.9%) use different teaching methods for slow learners, with a small percentage (13.6%) expressing uncertainty and disagreement. Most (65.4%) plan and modify instructional approaches to promote student attention, while a small percentage (14.8%) express uncertainty and disagreement. A significant portion (77.8%) engage in question-answering to help students learn, while a small percentage (7.4%) express uncertainty and disagreement. Most (65.4%) use classroom activities that help students learn, while a small percentage (13.6%) express uncertainty and disagreement. Most (61.7%) believe they possess sufficient knowledge about effective classroom management.

The majority of prospective teachers (66.7%) believe they have sufficient knowledge of all assessment techniques, while a small percentage (16%) express uncertainty and disagreement. Most (81.5%) assign class presentations to students, while a small percentage (7.4%) express uncertainty and disagreement. Most (59.3%) assign projects to students, while a small percentage (16%) express uncertainty and disagreement. A small percentage (42%) assign more numbers to their favorite students, while a small percentage (24.7%) express uncertainty and disagreement. Most (53.1%) use objective type tests for student assessments, while a small percentage (16%) express uncertainty and disagreement (Imran, et al., 2023).

A majority of prospective teachers (58%) use subjective tests for student assessment, while a small percentage (16.1%) express uncertainty and disagreement. The majority (66.7%) use various types of questions, including MCQs, short answers, and essay questions, while a small percentage (7.4%) express uncertainty and disagreement. A majority (76.5%) provide complete feedback to students about their assessment performance, while a small percentage (7.4%) express uncertainty and disagreement. A majority (61.8%) use class feedback to improve teaching strategies, while a small percentage (13.6%) express uncertainty and disagreement. A majority (72.9%) maintain proper records of student performance, while a small percentage (14.8%) express uncertainty and disagreement.

Correlation

Table 2: Relationship between the national professional teaching standard such as subject matter knowledge, instructional planning and strategies, assessment and growth and development

Variables	1	2	3	4
Growth and Development	-			
Subject Matter Knowledge	.614**	-		
Instructional Planning and Strategies	.812**	.665**	-	
Assessment	.648**	.584**	.709**	-

Note. N = 82

*p < .05, **p < .001

The above table demonstrates the total number of respondents which is denoted by N, significance value denoted by p and Pearson correlation value. Pearson Correlation is denoted by r. Therefore, findings revealed that there is a positive correlation between the growth and development and the national professional teaching standard 1 subject matter knowledge. The relationship between the growth and development and the subject matter knowledge is statistically significant, positive and strong because ($r = .614$, $p < .001$). Moreover, there is a positive correlation between the growth and development and the national professional teaching standard 2 instructional planning and strategies. The relationship between the growth and development and the instructional planning and strategies is statistically significant, positive and strong because ($r = .812$, $p < .001$). Furthermore, there is a positive correlation between the growth and development and the national professional teaching standard 3 assessment. The relationship between the growth and development and assessment is statistically significant, positive and strong because ($r = .648$, $p < .001$). Hence, results revealed that national professional standards such as subject matter knowledge, instructional planning and strategies and assessment are positively correlated with growth and development of prospective teachers.

Regression

Hypothesis 1: There is no any correlation between National Professional Teaching Standard (NPTS) subject matter and prospective teachers' growth and development in Baluchistan.

Table 3: Linear Regression of subject matter knowledge on prospective teachers' growth and development

Variable	<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	β	<i>t-value</i>
Constant	.974***	.204		
Subject Matter Knowledge	.617***	.089	.614	6.956
R ²	.377			

Note. * indicates significance $p < .001$.

The above table demonstrates the impact of national professional teaching standard subject matter knowledge on prospective teachers' growth and development. Therefore, findings shows that subject matter knowledge explained $R^2 = .377$ almost 38% of the variance in the growth and development of prospective teachers. Moreover, the model was fit, $F(1, 80) = 48.387$, $p < .05$ and it indicates that relationship between subject matter knowledge and growth and development of student teacher is statistically significant. Hence, result revealed that hypothesis of current study is rejected that there is no any correlation between National Professional Teaching Standard (NPTS) subject matter and prospective teachers' growth and development in Baluchistan because result revealed that subject matter is positively correlated with prospective teachers' growth and development in Baluchistan.

Hypothesis 2: National Professional Teaching Standard (NPTS) instructional planning and strategies has not significant relationship with prospective teachers' growth and development in Baluchistan.

Table 4: Linear Regression of Instructional Planning and Strategies on prospective teachers' growth and development

Variable	<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	β	<i>t-value</i>
Constant	.659***	.141		
Instructional Planning and Strategies	.769***	.062	.812	12.425
R ²	.659			

Note. * indicates significance $p < .001$.

The above table demonstrates the impact of national professional teaching standard instructional planning and strategies on prospective teachers' growth and development. Therefore, findings shows that instructional planning and strategies explained $R^2 = .659$ almost 66% of the variance in the growth and development of prospective teachers. Moreover, the model was fit, $F(1, 80) = 154.379$, $p < .05$ and it indicates that relationship between instructional planning and strategies and growth and development of student teacher is statistically significant. Hence, result revealed that hypothesis of current study is rejected that National Professional Teaching Standard (NPTS) instructional planning and strategies has not significant relationship with prospective teachers' growth and development in Baluchistan because result revealed that instructional planning and strategies is positively correlated with prospective teachers' growth and development in Baluchistan.

Hypothesis 3: There is no any relationship between National Professional Teaching Standards (NPTS) assessment and prospective teachers' growth and development in Baluchistan.

Table 5: Linear Regression of Assessment on prospective teachers' growth and development

Variable	<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>β</i>	<i>t-value</i>
Constant	.765 ^{***}	.213		
Instructional Planning and Strategies	.680 ^{***}	.089	.648	7.615
R ²	.420			

Note. * indicates significance $p < .001$.

The above table demonstrates the impact of national professional teaching standard assessment on prospective teachers' growth and development. Therefore, findings shows that assessment explained $R^2 = .420$ almost 42% of the variance in the growth and development of prospective teachers. Moreover, the model was fit, $F(1, 80) = 57.991$, $p < .05$ and it indicates that relationship between assessment and growth and development of student teacher is statistically significant. Hence, result revealed that hypothesis of current study is rejected that there is no any relationship between National Professional Teaching Standards (NPTS) assessment and prospective teachers' growth and development in Baluchistan because result revealed that assessment is positively correlated with prospective teachers' growth and development in Baluchistan.

Reliability

Table 6

Variables	Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Subject Matter Knowledge	8	.744
Instructional Planning and Strategies	10	.819
Assessment	9	.722
Growth and development	8	.718

The Cronbach's alpha was used to test the reliability of variables. The table demonstrates the factors, items of variables and Cronbach's Alpha value. Therefore, findings show that eight (8) items were included in subject matter knowledge and $\alpha = .744$. Furthermore, ten (10) items were included in instructional planning and strategies and $\alpha = .819$. Moreover, nine (9) items were included in assessment and $\alpha = .722$ and eight (8) items were included in growth and development and $\alpha = .718$. Hence, results revealed that tool was reliable because alpha value of both all variables is above .7. So, reliable tool was used in this study.

4. Discussion

The results of the survey indicate that a sizable majority of prospective teachers (86.4%) are aware of the goals and objectives related to the subjects they will be teaching. This observation indicates a propensity to see the value of understanding the intended outcomes of learning sessions, which can lead to improved pedagogical approaches.

Nearly 91% of prospective teachers believe they are up to date on the core ideas and theories of their fields of study. This conclusion is significant because it demonstrates a commitment to maintaining knowledge and expertise in their respective fields.

Regarding the incorporation of real-world experiences into their teaching practices, a substantial proportion of prospective teachers, or 58.0%, reported being highly skilled at incorporating real-world situations into their subject areas. Even though the current percentage is a good result, there is still room for improvement. The integration of tangible examples and real-world applications can enhance students' understanding and engagement with the material.

In relation to the integration of subjects with other disciplines, it was found that approximately 56.8% of aspiring educators reported actively establishing connections between their teaching subjects and other fields of study. Interdisciplinary education plays a crucial role in cultivating a comprehensive comprehension of information and its interconnections.

According to the data, a sizable fraction of prospective teachers use a variety of assessment techniques (66.7%) and have a positive attitude toward classroom dynamics management techniques (73.8%). However, it is crucial to recognize that there is a great deal of uncertainty in these fields, which calls for more study and the development of expert knowledge.

Approximately 69.1% of aspiring educators indicated their utilization of technological resources as a means to enhance pupils' focus. This observation exemplifies the increasing inclination towards incorporating technology inside educational settings as a means of augmenting the process of knowledge acquisition.

A considerable percentage of would-be teachers (76.5%) provide in-depth feedback to students about their exam results. However, there is room for improvement when it comes to assigning homework that corresponds with classroom instruction and using student feedback to enhance instructional strategies.

The aim of this study was to investigate the relationship between the national professional teaching standards (NPTS) and prospective teachers' growth and development. Therefore, three hypotheses were formulated to achieve the aim of this study. The findings show that subject matter knowledge, instructional planning and strategies and assessment are positively correlated with student teachers' growth and development.

The first hypothesis of this study was that there is no any correlation between National Professional Teaching Standard (NPTS) subject matter and prospective teachers' growth and development in Baluchistan. The result revealed that the hypothesis was

rejected and subject matter knowledge is positively correlated with prospective teachers' growth and development. The researcher Ball (2010) stated that teachers need to be modernized regarding comprehension in their respective subjects which can improve their growth and development (Oad, Khan & Khoso, 2020).

The second hypothesis of this study was that National Professional Teaching Standard (NPTS) instructional planning and strategies has not significant relationship with prospective teachers' growth and development in Baluchistan. The result revealed that the hypothesis was rejected and instructional planning and strategies is positively associated with prospective teachers' growth and development. Khalid et al. (2022) concluded that most of teachers adopt the application of Instructional Planning and Strategies with need for improvement in the skills development aspect. Moreover, Vanassche and Kelchtermans (2014) stated that Instructional Planning and Strategies is the key contribution to the development of teachers in their professional life.

The third hypothesis of this study was that there is no any relationship between National Professional Teaching Standards (NPTS) assessment and prospective teachers' growth and development in Baluchistan. The result revealed that the hypothesis was rejected and assessment is positively associated with prospective teachers' growth and development. According to a Paper on teacher assessment (2010) from National Education Association (NEA) assessment provides additional opportunities for teachers to learn and grow to become prospective teacher.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, it may be inferred that the aforementioned points support the notion that...

The results of the data analysis show that most prospective teachers have a positive attitude toward understanding the goals and purposes of the subject matter, keeping up with current knowledge, and utilizing a variety of teaching techniques. However, there are a few areas that still need improvement, such as the incorporation of real-world experiences, the effective use of technology, and the delivery of comprehensive feedback to students.

This research indicates that the National Professional Teaching Standards (NPTS) has had a positive effect on teachers' training progress in Baluchistan. The survey results suggest that there is a need to enhance the training process and consider additional measures in order to maximize the potential of this program and continue to improve the quality of education in the area.

6. Recommendations

The current study offers a set of recommendations targeted at enhancing pedagogical approaches among aspiring educators, based on the empirical evidence.

Career Advancement: Educate teachers through workshops and training sessions with the goal of improving their knowledge and pedagogical skills, especially in areas where

ambiguity has been found. Supporting the creation of interdisciplinary connections and the incorporation of real-world experiences into lesson plans.

The goal of technology integration is to encourage the effective use of technology in classrooms to increase student engagement and maximize their educational opportunities.

Key practices in the field of assessment include encouraging instructors to use assessment data to inform their teaching strategies and promoting a variety of assessment methods.

This initiative's goal is to provide support and access to a range of resources that could improve the application of effective classroom management techniques, ultimately promoting an ideal learning environment.

Peer learning entails giving aspiring teachers the opportunity to share and exchange successful teaching practices, thereby promoting a cooperative setting for learning and professional development.

It is essential to acknowledge and value the limitations that are inherent in this research. The survey was given to a specific group of prospective teachers, which may have limited its applicability to the larger community. It's also critical to take into account the possible influence of social desirability bias and self-reporting bias on the outcomes.

7. Future Research

Future research endeavors could potentially employ longitudinal studies to observe the evolution of teaching practices over an extended duration, thereby broadening the scope of the findings from this study. Furthermore, deeper insights into prospective educators' viewpoints and experiences may be obtained through focus groups or interviews.

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